

A new species of genus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Sichuan province of China

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Abstract

Sthenias (s. str.) *murzini* sp. n. close to *Sthenias gracilicornis* Gressitt, 1937 is described from Qingchenghou Shan Mountains (China, Sichuan). The distinguishing characters are discussed.

Key words

Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, new species, taxonomy, China.

Introduction

Several long-time regular expeditions of Russian entomologist Sergey Murzin to China allows him to create an enormous collection of Chinese insects. The most interesting part of that material is represented by Longicorn Beetles (Cerambycidae), which includes many new species. Now we begin a regular investigation of his beetles.

Materials and methods

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 – 30.5 mm 1:2.8 – 4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustration were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Taxonomical part

Family Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825

Tribe Pteropliini J. Thomson, 1860

Genus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840

Type species:

Lamia grisator Fabricius, 1787

Sthenias (s. str.) *murzini* Lazarev sp. n.

Figs. 1-3

Type material

Holotype, male, China, Sichuan prov., Qingcheng Hou

Shan Mts., 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 15.8.2004, S. Murzin leg. – collection of Maxim Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Description

A single male available; body generally brown, with very bright contrast white transverse band behind elytral middle, without black lines or spots along its posterior border.

Frons transverse with irregular scattered punctation, deeply concave between antennal tubercles; eyes deeply emarginated with a single row of ommatidia between dorsal and ventral lobes; genae about as long as ventral eye lobe; antennae 11-segmented, a little longer than body surpassing elytral apices by 9th apical joint; recumbent antennal pubescence brown with irregular small paler areas; with numerous erect setae along internal surface; 3rd antennal joint about as long as 4th, longer than 1st and much longer than 5th; prothorax transverse, about 1.14 times shorter than basal width, nearly parallel-sided, lateral sides slightly roundly exposed posteriorly, with very small, but distinct tubercle at anterior margin; pronotum totally brown without any white markings, with big scattered punctation, with a pair of wide round callosities at middle, bearing several big dots; elytra parallel-sided, slightly widened near apex, about 2.3 times longer than basal width, with a pair of distinct hairy tubercles anteriorly and here with very big dense punctation; contrast wide elytral band strongly triangularly emarginated anteriorly with irregular posterior margin; anterior margin of elytral

band with much denser white pubescence, becoming a little darker posteriorly, with a narrow contrast curved white line near posterior margin; posterior elytral punctation much smaller than anterior; elytral apices strongly attenuated and each independently rounded, not angulated; legs short, with dense brown pubescence, with scattered pale spots; middle tibiae with distinct black brush; 1st joint of posterior tarsus about as long as 2nd and 3rd combined; 1st abdominal segment with a row of long and dense yellow setae along posterior margin; 2nd segment with a pair of deep oval depressions setose on the bottom; last abdominal tergite rounded, last abdominal sternite truncated; body length 13.5 mm, width: 4.0 mm.

Differential diagnosis

The genus was revised by Breuning (1962). The new species is close to *Sthenias gracilicornis* Gressitt, 1937 because of brown body with wide white elytral band and attenuated elytral apices, but here elytral band is rather contrast (in *S. gracilicornis* - with diffused anterior margin), elytra paler, with numerous black markings, with big black spots behind transverse elytral band, with a brush of black setae on elytral apices, besides male antennae are much longer than body. *Sthenias cylindricus* Gressitt, 1939 is also similar to the new species, but elytra much paler and transverse elytral band followed with black spots, pronotal callosities nearly indistinct.

Remark

A female of the new species (China, North Sichuan) was shown by A. Gorodinsky in http://www.gorodinski.ru/view_cerambycidae.php?id_cerambyx=328. It is very similar to the holotype because of same body color, thoracic shape and elytral design, but antennae short, about as long as body.

Distribution. The new species is only known from the type locality in Qingcheng Hou Shan Mts., 1450 m, 70 km to the north-west from Chengdu (China, Sichuan province).

Etymology. The species is dedicated to my friend - well-known Moscow entomologist, professional traveler and lucky insect collector Dr. Sergey Murzin, who collected the holotype.

Acknowledgement

I am very grateful to Sergey Murzin for applying me with the specimen for study.

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Figs 1-3. *Sthenias (s. str.) murzini* Lazarev **sp. n.**, holotype, male, 1 - dorsal view, 2 - lateral view, 3 - frontal view